

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN ORGANIZATIONAL CULTURE AND PERCEIVED QUALITY OF WORKING LIFE AMONG LOCAL GOVERNMENT EMPLOYEES

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Relationship between Organizational Culture and Perceived Quality of Working Life among Local Government Employees

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Abstract

This study examined the relationship between the perceived quality of working life and organizational culture among local government employees in Lubao, Pampanga, Philippines. To determine the variables and their relationships, a quantitative approach and descriptive-correlational study design were used. The respondents have been engaged at the local government agency for a minimum of one year. They are classified as either permanent or casual employees. No matter the age or gender of the participant, only 87 permanent workers and 85 casual employees met the requirements and were thus eligible to participate. The findings revealed that there was a high degree of perceived quality of working life among both permanent and temporary workers of the local administration. Job and career satisfaction are two of the psychosocial aspects that both respondents report having a high degree of. On the other hand, they deal with a great deal of stress on the job. The results of this research showed that among permanent workers, there is no correlation between organizational culture and their perceived of the quality of their working lives. On top of that, the organizational culture has a substantial impact on the way casual workers evaluate their quality of life on the job.

Keywords: *quality of work life, organizational culture, productivity program*

Introduction

Globalization, technological advances, political upheavals, and the COVID-19 pandemic are increasing competitiveness for organizations worldwide. In this fast-paced climate, human resource management is vital. Human resources are a company's working population. Because they provide their time, energy, skill, and knowledge to the company's objective, workers are its greatest asset. HR manages the company's human resources, handles employee concerns, and builds a productive, engaged, and talented workforce (Heathfield, 2020). Local governments in developing countries like the Philippines face poverty, law and order, climate change, and natural disasters (Calleja, 2018). COVID-19 is one of the main issues facing all LGUs. They must lead the battle against this illness and defend their population. A motivated, happy, and efficient team with the right expertise, skills, and resources may help organizations solve these issues. By following public personnel administration legislation and Civil Service Rules, the government may manage its people resources.

Local governments face poverty, law and order, climate change, and natural disasters in developing countries like the Philippines (Calleja, 2018). Covid-19 is one of the main difficulties that LGUs face. They must lead the campaign to combat this sickness and defend their populace. With motivated, happy, and efficient personnel with the right expertise, skills, and resources, organizations can effectively handle these issues. The government tracks its human resource management by following public personnel administration statutes and Civil Service Rules. In addition, public organizations, like LGUs, adhere to a strict hierarchical structure based on governing documents like constitutions, statutes, and memoranda, as opposed to the flat organizational models seen in private enterprises. Local governments in the Philippines were granted delegated rights and ability to make crucial decisions about the governance of their communities in 1991 with the passing of the Local Government Code. Innovation and structural shifts at the local level are facilitating the assumption of broader and more responsible responsibilities in local government (Legaspi, 2010). Public sector objectives and expectations are shaped by environmental factors such as political agendas, current policies, allotted funds, and appointed leadership. The public sector is recognized to prioritize social concerns over commercial ones (Barrow, 2019). Employees' perceptions of the agency's culture are shaped by all of these factors. Employees' shared values dictate their behavior, performance, and interactions with the organization's procedures; this is called organizational culture (Watkins, 2013). Publications and correlations of studies examining the agency culture, such as those of Tsai (2011), were made. Leadership conduct and employee job satisfaction were shown to be positively connected with corporate culture in this research. For this reason, it is critical for LGUs to foster an environment that values organizational culture while training and educating their staff.

Lubao LGU is a top Pampanga municipality that values its employees. The agency also received the Department of Interior and Local Government's Seal of Good Local Governance. Currently, there are 127 full-time and 123 part-time workers. Every agency employee brings distinct values and behaviors to the workplace. Thus, the researcher examined Lubao, Pampanga's Local Government Units' human resources difficulties by correlating workers' work life quality judgments with organizational culture. The agency may utilize this to launch a productivity program to teach people to be more productive and efficient to provide high-quality services. A strong human resource program, like a productivity program, may benefit the organization and its employees more than its cost. In the middle of the COVID-19 pandemic, workers may require the liberty to fill skill shortages and adjust to changing situations.

Research Questions

This study sought the relationship of the perceived quality of working life and organizational culture among local government

employees, the results of which will be utilized to propose a productivity program. Specifically, the study answered the following problems:

1. What is the perceived quality of working life among the respondents per employment status in terms of:
 - 1.1. general well – being;
 - 1.2. home-work interface;
 - 1.3. job and career satisfaction;
 - 1.4. control at work;
 - 1.5. working conditions; and
 - 1.6. stress at work?
2. What is the perception of the respondents in their organizational culture per employment status in terms of:
 - 2.1. managing change;
 - 2.2. achieving goals;
 - 2.3. coordinated teamwork;
 - 2.4. customer orientation; and
 - 2.5. cultural strength?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the perceived quality of working life and the organizational culture among:
 - 3.1. permanent employees; and
 - 3.2. casual employees?

Literature Review

Perceived Quality of Working Life

Quality of working life, according to Ogbuabor and Okoronkwo (2019), is workers' opinions of how their working conditions may suit their personal and job needs and their company goals. This term is almost 50 years old in academic literature. Quality of life encompasses this sub-concept. Historical discussions on working life quality focused on how employment affected workers' health and happiness. Employee-centric businesses understand workers better, which improves employee well-being, according to Martic (2020). Over time, organizations started to care for their employees' well-being and professional advancement to keep them longer. Sambantham & Venkatramaju (2016) changed the company's view of quality of life by redefining staff as assets. Mayo was one of the first to use the Quality of Work Life model to study workplace efficiency (Easton & Van Laar, 2018). It's the combination of organizational practices and employee satisfaction, motivation, involvement, and commitment. This happens when workers can meet essential personal needs at work. Companies that care about their employees' happiness try to make them feel protected, appreciated, respected, part of the team, accountable, and adaptable. Management is fair and helpful because it provides workers a voice in decisions that affect them and offers them the tools, they need to execute their jobs properly (Srivastava & Kanpur, 2014). According to Aranganathan and Sivarethnamohan (2012), work-life quality is crucial to a company. This involves improving worker safety, amenities, and supervisory relationships, which boost productivity and profit. Several definitions of "work life balance" emphasize job-related aspects. Some associate it with life satisfaction and personality, while others associate it with mental health (Easton & Van Laar, 2018).

Shukla et al. (2017) studied multi-specialty hospital workers' quality of work life and found that permanent employees with higher positions scored better in control at work, job and career satisfaction, and home-work interface. Imran (2011) found that job satisfaction connected with working life quality among construction craft workers. The two indicators are substantially associated, hence the study proposed that the company improve working conditions to boost employee job satisfaction. In a non-managerial employee research, Islam and Siengthai (2009) discovered that job satisfaction is positively and substantially connected with working life quality. Quality of working life is favorably connected with organizational performance; however, the correlation is not significant. In Kelbiso et al. (2017), demographics connected with nurses' job quality. Nursing quality of life was strongly correlated with educational level, monthly salary, working unit, and work environment. Gala et al. (2016) studied Region XI, Davao Region residents. When classified by sex and location, working life quality did not differ. However, political socialization and working life quality are linked. Bagtasos and Espere (2010) found that selected secondary school teachers in Davao City should reduce their work loads and hours to improve their work life and reduce stress. The quality of government workers' working lives was also studied. Amin (2012) revealed that professional growth and personal characteristics like demographics might improve public sector personnel' quality of life in Medan, Indonesia. This helped management learn how to improve work life for individuals and the company. Kim and Cho (2003) evaluated the quality of working life of Korean government and private sector workers. Government workers' working lives are far poorer than those in the private sector. According to the data, the most important factor is employee happiness in their work environment, thus the government should enhance it to keep workers happy and engaged. Additionally, Permarupan et al. (2013) examined the quality of work life in Malaysian public and private sector enterprises. It was linked to occupational participation and emotional commitment by researchers. The respondents' quality of working life was judged by fair and adequate remuneration, working circumstances, capabilities at work, possibilities at work, and organization atmosphere. Working circumstances, opportunity, and climate organization affected job participation and affective commitment more. According to Boone et al. (2019), higher education personnel have an average work life.

Organizational Culture

Culture is a company's norms, beliefs, attitudes, and practices that unify workers. Organizational personality is what it is (McNamara, 2006). Forsey (2018) identified it as an essential part of any workplace where the common vision improves the environment. Problem-solving defines the firm's link to its internal and external contexts (Joseph & Kibera, 2018). Company operations, employee attitudes, and objectives reflect this. It unites and improves organizational performance, according to Gochhayat et al. (2017). An organization's culture is equally crucial to its human resources. Kriemadis et al. (2008) examined the organizational culture of Greek hotel managers. The respondents ranked medium on managing change, attaining objectives, and cultural strength and high on coordinated cooperation and customer focus. Uzzo (2002) also investigated permanent academic personnel using the Organizational Culture Assessment Questionnaire (OCAQ). Employees rated high or very high in managing change, attaining objectives, coordinated cooperation, and customer orientation. Average cultural strength perception.

Ahmed and Shafiq (2014) examined how organizational culture affects telecom performance. Findings demonstrated that all organizational culture factors affect organizational performance perspectives. As Paschal & Nizam (2016) observed among Singapore Telecommunications workers, corporate culture like rituals, values, and heroes affects employee performance more than symbols. In Tsai (2011), organizational culture was linked to leadership behavior and work satisfaction among Taiwanese nurses. Leadership behavior and work satisfaction were highly connected with corporate culture. The Organizational Culture Assessment Questionnaire was used to analyze the organization culture of Ghanaian insurance workers by Selase et al. (2018). Employee work engagement is positively correlated with corporate culture. The research showed that management should adopt, develop, and perpetuate a positive culture to boost employee engagement. Racelis (2010) researched Philippine banking. A favorable association was found between company profitability and bank culture.

Ashpaoloye (2014) studied corporate culture and employee motivation in Calabarzon to improve leadership, innovation, and motivation. Results indicated Batangas, Lipa, and Tanauan concurred on organizational culture and motivation. Working connection predicts company culture best, according to study. Public agency organizational culture was also studied in the government. Schraeder et al. (2005) compared public and private sector organizational cultures. Despite commonalities, public sector cultural differences provide distinct hurdles for managers trying to adapt. With this, the researchers discussed how training and leading by example might promote cultural awareness and transformation in public organizations. Parker and Bradley's (2020) study of six Queensland public organizations' organizational cultures recommended that the public sector prioritize change, flexibility, outcomes, efficiency, and productivity over bureaucratic values. Barrow (2019) examined US government organizational culture among public health workers. Results showed that the local health department should use the NACCHO Roadmap for quality improvement, increase employee participation to improve horizontal integration, and adopt comprehensive approaches to address organizational culture and promote a new culture. In addition, Yosinta (2016) performed a dissertation to 480 public personnel in 16 Thai provinces. The research examined how organizational culture affects public sector performance management in Thai provincial administrations. Strong culture, participatory leadership, and suitable management help achieve Key Performance Indicators ratings. A balance between task-focused and people-focused leadership affects public service performance. Instead of a fundamental cultural change, the studies advised better public sector leadership and management.

Perceived Quality of Work Life and Organizational Culture

Multiple studies used these criteria to assess the quality of work life and organization culture of different organizations and businesses. Human resources cultures and employee well-being vary per firm. The quality of workers' working lives and corporate culture depend on several factors. Lowering stress may enhance work life in an organization. In a 2017 American Psychological Association-Harris Poll research, full-time workers experienced persistent job stress owing to organizational changes. According to Wisse and Sleebos (2016), change causes stress when it affects workers' sense of self and causes uncertainty, which is a characteristic of corporate culture. In addition, Ogbonnaya (2019) showed that cooperation might stress and push workers to perform well. Valizadeh and Ghahremani (2012) studied the link between company culture and employee well-being. Well-being, work-life balance, and working circumstances impact workers' experiences at firms, according to research. Well-being affects workers' view of an organization's cultural strength, according to Martin (2020). Balance between home and professional life improves business culture and employee performance, according to Sheppard (2016). To prevent and overcome change resistance, Williams (2021) proposed considering employee work-life balance while implementing change. Pomaki et al. (2004) found that working environments affect workers' perception of organizational objectives.

The research by Kuokkanen et al. (2009) found that organizational changes affect employee work satisfaction, and that people management is needed to adapt to these changes. Torkan and Vanani (2017) studied 295 hospital nurses in descriptive-correlation research. Results demonstrated a favorable correlation between work life quality and all organizational culture factors. To improve nurses' work-life quality, an organizational culture that is collaborative and compatible with staff is needed. In Ruggiero et al. (2011), 145 Korean university hospital nurses were studied for quality of work-life, organizational culture, and organizational effectiveness. The findings showed substantial relationships between respondents' work-life quality, company culture, and organizational success. Rahmawati and Setiawati (2017) studied non-medical hospital workers in Indonesia and found a correlation between work life quality, organizational culture, and job satisfaction.

Synthesis

Literature and research may reinforce study findings, hence the following studies supplied information comparable to the study variables. Valizadeh and Ghahremani (2012) studied the same factors to determine the association between company culture and employee quality of life. These two factors are directly and significantly related. Valizadeh and Ghahremani (2012) surveyed 796 workers of Iran's Islamic Azad University of Tabriz (IAUT). In this research, the respondents are 87 regular and 85 casual workers of the Lubao, Pampanga Local Government Unit in the Philippines. Because the two research projects' respondents are from different sectors and countries, the findings can only be applied to a sample. Additionally, this research compares the factors to their work status, such as permanent and casual appointments. This study will result in a recommended human resource program based on its findings and debate, unlike the study of Valizadeh and Ghahremani (2012) solely examine correlations and relationships between variables. Ruggiero et al. (2011) also examined organizational culture and work life of 145 Korean University Hospital personnel in South Korea. They also associated respondents' education and years in service, but this research correlated them to their work position. Unlike this research, they added organizational effectiveness and did not build a human resource program. Bagtasos and Espere (2010) evaluated the quality of working life among selected secondary teachers in Davao City. The respondents had a great quality of working life in terms of managing their personal and professional lives, although workloads, job expectations, and working hours could be lowered. Racelis (2010) analyzed employee organizational culture in the Philippine banking sector. A favorable association was found between company profitability and bank culture. This research associated employee quality of life with corporate culture, unlike previous studies.

Methodology

Research Design

The study employed a descriptive – correlational type of research to identify and describe the respondent's perceived quality of working life in terms of job and career satisfaction, working conditions, general well – being, home-work interface, stress at work and control at work and the perception of the respondent's organizational culture in terms of managing change, achieving goals, coordinated teamwork, customer orientation and cultural strength in accordance with their employment status which are regular and casual appointments. At the same time, this study examined the relationship between all the variables.

This type of research design is considered a quantitative approach which is defined by Alfieri (2015) as a type of research that relies on measuring variables using a numerical system and by finding its relationships and associations without looking for its causal effect and so, this approach has been chosen as an appropriate research method. Standardized tests were used as a method of data collection which allows large sample size in producing quantitative data that can be analyzed by statistical computer programs.

Respondents

The sampling technique which was utilized in this study is the purposive sampling technique. It is when the participants are selected from the population that best suits the purpose of the study (Singh, 2018).

The respondents of this study are the employees of the Local Government Unit of Lubao. Since the study used the purposive sampling technique, a set of criteria was identified by the researcher to further strengthen and support the results study. Only eighty-seven (87) permanent employees and eighty-five (85) casual employees were selected and qualified to participate.

The respondents are presently employed at the said local government agency for at least one (1) year. They have an employment status of either casual or permanent. This is regardless of the participant's gender or age. Based on the criteria

Instruments

To this study, the researcher used the Work-Related Quality of Life Scale (WRQoL) and the Organizational Culture Assessment Questionnaire (OCAQ).

Work-Related Quality of Life Scale (WRQoL)

The Work – Related Quality of Life Scale is used to measure the perceived quality of working life of the employees as measured through six psychosocial sub-factors. This scale which was developed by Simon Easton and Darren Van Laar in 2018 is used by individuals, organizations, and consultants as well as researchers as an aid to assessing and understanding the quality of working life of working people. It aims to capture the essence of an individual's work experience in the broadest sense. It assesses Quality of Working Life by six core factors which includes Job and Career Satisfaction, General Well – Being, Home-Work Interface, Stress at Work, Control at Work and Working Conditions. The Factor 1- Job and Career Satisfaction (JCS) contain six (6) items such as “I am satisfied with the career opportunities available to me at the organization” (Item 5) and had a sub- scale reliability of .86. While the Factor 2 - General Well – Being (GWB) which has also six (6) items such as “Generally things work out well for me” (Item 18) and had a sub- scale reliability of .82. The Factor 3 - Home-Work Interface (HWI) contained three (3) items such as “My current working hours/patterns suit my personal circumstances” (Item 17) and had a scale reliability of .82. While Factor 4 - Stress at Work (SAW) contained two (2) items such as “I often feel under pressure at work” (Item 7) and had a sub-scale reliability of .81. The Factor 5 –

Control at Work (CAW) is loaded with three (3) items such as “I am involved in decisions that affect me in my own area of work” (Item 12) and had a sub-scale reliability of .81. Lastly, Factor 6 – Working Conditions (WCS) is being represented by three (3) items such as “The working conditions are satisfactory” (Item 9) and has a .75 sub-scale reliability. While the test-retest reliability of the scale and its individual factors showed strong, significant, positive intra-class correlation and have an over-all reliability of .87. Moreover, it also has an excellent convergent validity with 0.83 when the Overall Work-Related Quality of Life Scale was correlated with Overall Warr Job Satisfaction Scale.

The questionnaire has 24 items although the scale is originally consisted of 23 items. The last item is “I am satisfied with the overall quality of my working life” which is a general question which was added to serve as an indicator of the validity and reliability of the scale and its factors. Item scores in the WRQoL are derived from a 5-point Likert scale from Strongly Disagree (1) to Strongly Agree (5). The individual factor scores will be calculated by taking the average of the item scores which represent the factors with the scores reversed for the three negatively phrased items. While the overall work-related quality of life of the participants is the average of the six factors scores. Moreover, the interpretation of the sub-scale scores will be classified into lower, average, and higher (Easton & Van Laar, 2018). The following are the norms of the Work – Related Quality of Life (WRQoL) Scale.

Range	GWB	HWI	JCS	CaW	WC	SaW	Overall WRQoL
High	22.00-30.00	12.00-15.00	23.00-36.00	12.00-15.00	12.00-15.00	6.00-10.00	82.00-115.00
Average	20.01- 21.99	10.00-11.99	20.00-22.99	10.00-11.99	11.00-11.99	5.00-5.99	72.00 – 81.99
Low	1.00-20.00	1.00-9.99	1.00-19.99	1.00-9.99	1.00-10.99	1.00-4.99	23.00-71.99

Organizational Culture Assessment Questionnaire

The Organizational Culture Assessment Questionnaire is a 30-item scale developed by Marshall Sashkin in 1990 which measures how employees of an organization perceive the culture of their work environment in five (5) areas and functions which are Managing Change, Achieving Goals, Coordinated Teamwork, Customer Orientation and Cultural Strength. This questionnaire was based on Dr. Talcott Parsons’s framework and theory of action in social system wherein organizations must carry out crucial functions to survive for any substantial length of time. Each of its sub-scales consists of six (6) items and statements. The Scale 1 is the Managing Change which assesses the degree on how the respondents see the organization as effective in managing change and adapting to it. It has .66 reliability and one of the statements is “People are flexible and adaptable when changes are necessary” (Item 1). Scale 2 is Achieving Goals which describes the degree to which shared values support improvement and achievement rather than status quo. The reliability of this sub-scale is .84 and part of the items which represents it is “Individuals and teams have clearly defined goals that relate to the goals or mission of the organization” (Item 2). While the Scale 3 – Coordinated Teamwork describes the extent which the shared value of collaboration is visible. Its reliability is .76 and an example of questionnaire item which consist of it is “Teams often lack the authority needed to get the job effectively” (Item 3). Scale 4 is the Customer Orientation which assesses if the organization directs its activities toward identifying and meeting the needs and goals of its clients. Its sub-scale reliability is .74 and one of its items is “We give the highest priority and support to meeting the needs of clients and customers and solving their problems” (Item 4). Lastly, the Scale 5 is Cultural Strength on which employees agree on values and examining if the meta- values are present such as the belief that people should support their views with facts. The reliability of the sub-scale is .84 and one of the statements that represents it is “People value and make use of one another’s unique strengths and different abilities” (Item 5) (Sashkin& Rosenbach, 2013). This questionnaire is a five-point Likert scale which ask the respondent to agree or disagree with the items from 5 - completely true, 4 – mostly true, 3 – partly true, 2 – slightly true and 1 – not true. Each sub-scales range from six (6) to thirty

(30) points (Uzzo, 2002)

The following are the norms of the Organizational Culture Assessment Questionnaire, to wit:

Range	MC	AG	CT	CO	CS	Overall OC
Very High	30	28.00-30.00	25.00-30.00	25.00-30.00	26.00-30.00	119+
High	26.00-29.99	23.00-27.99	24.00-27.99	21.00-24.99	22.00-25.99	108.00- 118.99
Average	19.00-25.99	16.00-22.99	18.00-23.99	15.00-20.99	17.00-21.99	87.00-107.99
Low	15.00-18.99	11.00-15.99	14.00-17.99	11.00-14.99	13.00-16.99	76.00-86.99
Very Low	6.00 -14.99	6.00-10.99	6.00-13.99	6.00-10.99	6.00-12.99	3.00-75.99

Procedure

A formal request letter signed by the researcher was forwarded to the Head of the Agency for the approval. After the confirmation, the researcher identified the qualified respondents based on the set of criteria. In line with the COVID – 19 pandemics in the country, direct contact to the respondents is not possible. Hence, after the participants agreed, the researcher administered the Work – Related Quality of Life Scale and the Organizational Culture Assessment Questionnaire by sending them the Google Forms through the link provided by the researcher. In this link, the informed consent and confidentiality agreement is indicated followed by the standardized questionnaires. Instructions were also given before the test administration by sending them set of guidelines which they should follow during the test administration. The respondents were guided by the researcher through phone calls whenever they have concerns with the process. The data was analyzed using a quantitative technique, namely by using the Pearson correlation coefficient (r).

Ethical Considerations

All participants provide informed consent. An informed consent form including information on the methods, rewards, and dangers of involvement, an explanation of how to get the study findings, voluntary participation, and contact information for the researchers involved. A rationale was delivered prior to the first part of the instrumentation, and participants were informed about the overall aim and method of their involvement in the study. The researchers promised the participants that any relevant personal data information they supplied was highly appreciated in accordance with the Philippines' Data Privacy Act. Furthermore, a confidentiality declaration and commitment to ethical research norms formed the basis of this study project.

Results and Discussion

Problem 1. What is the perceived quality of working life of the respondents per employment status in terms of: general well – being, home-work interface, job and career satisfaction, control at work, working conditions, and stress at work?

Table 1 presents the perceived quality of working life of the permanent and casual employees of the Local Government Unit of Lubao. Based on the findings, both the permanent and casual employees exhibited high levels of job and career satisfaction with mean scores of 24.28 and 24.51, respectively. This indicates that the respondents are contented with their jobs and prospects at work. They feel good and have a sense of achievement and fulfillment with their potentials at work. The permanent employees are satisfied with their positions since they are secured with their appointments at the local government. No one can remove them from their positions unless they resigned, retired or found guilty with an administrative case.

Table 1
Perceived Quality of Working Life per Employment Status

Psychosocial Factors	PERMANENT			CASUAL			
	MEAN	STDDEV	Interpretation	MEAN	STDDEV	Interpretation	
General Well- Being (GWB)	23.07	3.266	High	23.02	2.948	High	
Home – Work Interface (HWI)	11.44	1.866	Average	11.93	1.765	Average	
Job and Career Satisfaction (JCS)	24.28	3.361	High	24.51	2.860	High	
Control at Work (CaW)	10.98	2.194	Average	10.87	1.811	Average	
Working Condition (WC)	11.77	1.815	Average	11.78	1.459	Average	
Stress at Work (SaW)	6.13	1.598	High	5.91	1.540	Average	
Overall WRQoL	91.63	10.987	High	91.92	9.292	High	
<i>Legend:</i>	<i>GWB</i>	<i>HWI</i>	<i>JCS</i>	<i>CaW</i>	<i>WC</i>	<i>SaW</i>	<i>Overall WRQoL</i>
<i>High</i>	22.00-30.00	12.00-15.00	23.00-36.00	12.00-15.00	12.00-15.00	6.00-10.00	82.00 – 115.00
<i>Average</i>	20.01- 21.99	10.00-11.99	20.00-22.99	10.00-11.99	11.00-11.99	5.00-5.99	72.00 – 81.99
<i>Low</i>	1.00-20.00	1.00-9.99	1.00-19.99	1.00-9.99	1.00-10.99	1.00-4.99	23.00-71.99

Similar to the study of Shukla et al. (2017) to the hospital employees, it has been found that regular and full-time employees have high job and career satisfaction level in their organization. While despite of the employment status of the casual employees, results showed high in this psychosocial factor because they enjoy working and pushing themselves to be one of the best employees. They are striving to have advancement with their career in the local government. Their perceived work experiences made them have the positive attitude towards their jobs.

Unlike with the study of Ntisa et al. (2016) wherein it was found that employees under fixed-term and contract have lower job satisfaction which means that these employees are not contented with what they are doing in their organization. The organization should further sustain and maintain the level of satisfaction among the employees since according to Imran (2011) and Islam and Siengthai (2009) quality of working life is positively and significantly correlated with the job satisfaction of the employees. This is also in support with Herzberg's two factor theories wherein he stated that employees should be satisfied with motivator factors that are intrinsic to the job such as job content, the work itself and responsibility at work in order to have a good quality of working life among the employees (Easton & Van Laar, 2012).

Moreover, as shown in the table, findings revealed that permanent employees have high level of stress at work with a mean score of 6.13 while casual employees scored 5.91 which is interpreted as average. This indicates that permanent employees experience and see stress and pressure with their work experiences. In the study of Edwards (2009), findings showed that permanent employees of higher

education have high level of stress at their respective work which is similar to this study. Bhui et al. (2016) found that physical environment, workloads and job demands are relevant factors to the stress at work of government employees. In this study, the demand of the job among permanent employees is high because most of them are appointed to different technical and crucial positions in the local government. While the casual employees, despite of having an interpretation of average, the score is in the borderline between high and average. This indicates that they are also experiencing stress and pressure in the local government. Due to the additional responsibilities which are being passed from the national government to the local government, demands of the job in the organization continue to increase. Added duties and responsibilities are being assigned even to the casual employees in the local government which causes them to experience pressure do their job effectively. In the study of Bagtasos and Espere (2010) to selected secondary school teachers in Davao City, findings revealed that to improve the quality of work life of the respondents and to reduce their stress level, findings suggested that the respondents should reduce their work loads and working hours. This is why the organization should improve this psychosocial factor that affects the productivity of the employees.

Furthermore, Table 1 shows that permanent and casual employees have high level of general well-being with mean scores of 23.07 and 23.02, respectively. This indicates that the respondents feel good and contented with their psychological well-being and general physical health aspects. Which is according to Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs Theory, individual should be satisfied with their safety needs such as their health in order to achieve self-actualization and be satisfied with their lives (Narehan, et al., 2014). Martic (2020) stated that the employee well-being is when the employer understands its employees in the holistic perspective by having an employee-centric organization wherein the Local Government Unit of Lubao is known for giving proper regards with their employees. The organization focuses on their employees' well-being because the head of the organization believes that good public service comes with taking care of its human resource. Just like in the study of Sambantham and Venkatramaju (2016) where the organization associate the quality of life as a positive phenomenon by considering their employees as an asset instead of expense.

While in home – work interface, the permanent employees have 11.44 mean score and 11.93 mean score for casual employees which are both interpreted as average. This indicates that the respondents should improve their balance between their personal and professional lives. Although both scores are in the upper limit section of the average interpretation, the organization should still promote and encourage the employees to balance their job and personal activities. This is unlike with the studies of Shukla et al. (2017) and Bagtasos and Espere (2010) where results showed that the employees have high level of home-work interface domain whereas they can juggle their time between work and life. While in control at work, the permanent and casual employees scored average with a mean score of 10.98 and 10.87, respectively, which indicates that the respondents are not given enough freedom to join with the decision making that involves their work situation. In the statement of Srivastava and Kanpur (2014), to have a high level of quality of work life, the management should treat the employees in a fair and supportive manner by offering them the opportunity to participate in decisions affecting them which will empower the employees to carry on with their tasks. At the same time, Table 1 also shows a mean score of 11.77 in working conditions among permanent employees and a mean score of 11.78 to casual employees. This suggests an average level of satisfaction among the respondents when it come to their fundamental resources, working conditions and security necessary to do their job effectively. The organization should improve the working conditions of the respondents since Kelbiso et al. (2017) examined the relationship of quality of working life among nurses to their working conditions like monthly income, working unit and the work environment. Findings found that working conditions are strong predictors of quality of working life.

Overall, the permanent and casual employees of the Local Government scored high level of perceived quality of working life with mean scores of 91.63 and 91.92, respectively. This signifies that the perceived holistic experiences of the respondents are good which made them feel satisfied with their quality of working life in the organization. This is unlike with the study of Boone et al. (2019) wherein it was found that the employees of higher institution have an average overall quality of working life which means that the management should take necessary steps and measures to improve the employees' experiences in the organization.

Problem 2. What is the perception of the respondents in their organizational culture per employment status in terms of: managing change, achieving goals, coordinated teamwork, customer orientation, and cultural strength?

Table 2 shows that both casual and permanent employees perceive that the organization have high level of customer orientation with mean scores of 24. 20 and 23.25, respectively and a low level of managing change with 19.79 and 20.26 mean scores. In accordance with the Theory of Action in Social Systems by Dr. Talcott Parson, he suggested that all organizations must carry out crucial factors, values of the culture and social norms and orders for them to be able to survive in a substantial length of time (Adams and Sydie, 2002). Hence, in this study, the respondents see the Local Government Unit of Lubao as an organization that has basic and strategic values that support an effective customer orientation and directed toward identifying and meeting the needs and goals of the customers. Since the organization is a government agency which offers public service, the administration focuses on proving good quality of service to its constituents. With this regard, both the permanent and casual employees are aware that the local government exists because of the people of Lubao. This is the same as the findings found in the study of Kriemadis et al. (2008) in which the employees scored high in the customer orientation domain which means that the organization is also a customer-oriented establishment. Unlike with the study of Uzzo (2002) in which the employees of a private institution showed an average score in this domain wherein the organization should promote values that are beneficial to their customers.

While average score in managing change and the lowest score among all of the domains of both the permanent and casual employees

signifies that the organization should provide improvements on how to properly apply and deal with changes within the organization. In the study of Schraeder et al. (2005), changes in the public sector were examined and it was found that public sector’s culture creates unique challenges for managers who try to evoke changes. With the findings, they provided a perspective on the application of training and leading by example as an effective method in promoting culture awareness and bringing culture change in the public organizations. This is in relation with Albert Bandura’s Social Learning Theory (1977), according to him, the environment and culture play a very important role to the employees of an organization. The working environment should be professional and the surroundings must be in a way that the employees can learn from them because he stated that behaviors can be acquired by observing and imitating others. While both the permanent and casual employees scored high in cultural strength with 23.15 and 22.33 mean scores which means that the respondents perceive the local government as an organization that has strong shared values which people agree such as the belief that everyone should support their views with facts. This is unlike the studies of Kriemadis et al. (2008) and Uzzo (2002) in which the respondents obtained average in their cultural strength domain which means that the organizations which their respondents are employed must strengthen their shared values and norms. In the Local Government Unit of Lubao, since most of the permanent and casual employees know each other and have been together for years, they were able to build a strong and holistic beliefs, values and norms that are beneficial to the employees and clients.

Table 2
Organizational Culture per Employment Status

Domains	PERMANENT			CASUAL		
	MEAN	STDDEV	Interpretation	MEAN	STDDEV	Interpretation
Managing Change (MC)	19.79	3.210	Average	20.26	2.391	Average
Achieving Goals (AG)	22.01	2.979	Average	21.16	2.414	Average
Coordinated Teamwork (CT)	22.79	3.257	Average	21.58	3.001	Average
Customer Orientation (CO)	24.20	2.778	High	23.25	2.992	High
Cultural Strength (CS)	23.15	3.164	High	22.33	2.710	High
Overall OC	119.94	12.170	Very High	108.58	11.041	High

Legend:	MC	AG	CT	CO	CS	Overall OC
Very High	30	28-30	25-30	25-30	26-30	119+
High	26-29	23=27	24-27	21-24	22-25	108-118
Average	19-25	16-22	18-23	15-20	17-21	97-107
Low	15-18	11-15	14-17	11-14	13-16	76-86
Very Low	6-14	6-10	6-13	6-10	6-12	3-75

Moreover, the permanent and casual employees scored average in achieving goals ($x=22.01$, $x= 21.16$) and coordinated teamwork ($x= 22.79$, $x= 21.58$) domains. This implies that the organization should improve their values of supporting improvement and achievement in reaching the organizational goals and promoting coordination and collaboration among employees. Similar with the study of Kriemadis et al. (2008) wherein the findings produced the same interpretation of average score as this study.

Overall, findings suggested that the perception of the permanent and casual employees in their organizational culture is high. The employees perceive that the organization helps them in promoting an effective organizational culture in the agency. Unlike with the study of Barrow (2019) to public health employees wherein findings showed that the respondents are not satisfied with their culture and that the researcher suggested the organization to promote culture change and adapt comprehensive approach that will address the factors in organizational culture. Also, in the study of Parker and Bradley (2020), findings from the employees suggested that public sectors should depart from the traditional bureaucratic values and adopt a greater emphasis on change, flexibility, outcomes, efficiency and productivity.

Problem 3. Is there a significant relationship between the perceived quality of working life and the organizational culture among: permanent employees and casual employees?

Table 3 shows positive strong correlation between stress at work and managing change domain ($r=.288$, $p\text{-value} = .007$) of the permanent employees. This indicates that when the level of stress at work increases, the perception of the respondents on how the organizations manage change also increases. Boyle (2020) discussed in an article that when it comes to organizational change, leaders play an important role in using the employees’ behaviors in setting up a tone on what is acceptable within the organization. The leadership decides whether what the organization says and what the employees see align with each other since leaders are the

implementers of the different strategies in imposing organizational changes. However, Brooks (2017) stated that even though change is common and inevitable in the workplace, sometimes, the leaders in the organizations underestimate the impact of these changes on the employees such as the stress and pressure that may occur in the process.

Table 3
Relationship between Managing Change Domain and Perceived Quality of Working Life per Employment Status

		PERMANENT			Psychosocial Factors of WRQoL		CASUAL				
<i>r</i>	<i>p-value</i>	Interpretation	Decision	Conclusion			<i>r</i>	<i>p-value</i>	Interpretation	Decision	Conclusion
.161	.136	Positive weak relationship	Accept Ho	Not Significant	General Well- Being (GWB)		.504**	.000	Positive moderate relationship	Reject Ho	Significant
.140	.198	Positive weak relationship	Accept Ho	Not Significant	Home – Work Interface (HWI)		.444**	.000	Positive moderate relationship	Reject Ho	Significant
.044	.685	Positive very weak relationship	Accept Ho	Not Significant	Job and Career Satisfaction (JCS)		.518**	.000	Positive Strong Relationship	Reject Ho	Significant
.067	.537	Positive very weak relationship	Accept Ho	Not Significant	Control at Work (CaW)		.291**	.007	Positive moderate relationship	Reject Ho	Significant
.149	.167	Positive weak relationship	Accept Ho	Not Significant	Working Condition (WC)		.406**	.000	Positive moderate relationship	Reject Ho	Significant
.288**	.007	Positive moderate relationship	Reject Ho	Significant	Stress at Work (SaW)		.210*	.053	Positive weak relationship	Accept Ho	Not Significant

**Correlation Significance at 0.01 (2-tailed)

*Correlation Significance at 0.05 (2-tailed)

Coefficient of correlation: ±1.00 (Perfect Relationship); ±0.76 – ± 0.99 (Very Strong Relationship); ±0.51- ±0.75 (Strong Relationship); ±0.26 - ±0.50 (Moderate Relationship); ± 0.11- ±0.25 (Weak Relationship); ±0.01 – ±0.10(Very Weak Relationship); ±0.00 (No Relationship)

These findings in the study signify that whenever the organization imposes change, the leaders should assess first the impact it may lead on its employees. As similar to the result of the study conducted by the American Psychological Association (2017) wherein the individuals employed full-time reported chronic work stress due to changes in the organization. Moreover, in the study of Wisse and Sleebos (2016), findings suggested that change leads to stress when the change has consequences that affect the sense of self of the employees which leads to feelings of uncertainty.

In this study, the permanent employees were found to have high level of stress based on their perceived quality of working life and an average level of effectiveness of the organization in adapting and managing change. In the Local Government Unit of Lubao, changes happen in the workplace due to the different perspectives and leadership skills of the Local Chief Executives and other officials who are being elected by its constituents. Permanent employees in this organization are known for holding technical key positions and have been in the public service for years. While recently, the Local Government Unit of Lubao elected a new Local Chief Executive in 2019 after the previous Local Chief Executive finished her term (PeoPlaid, 2020). With this major change, a lot of modifications followed which is why the findings suggested high level of stress at work to permanent employees. Unlike with the results found in casual employees wherein it shows that managing change has no significant relationship with stress at work ($r=.210$, $p\text{-value}=.053$) which indicates that changes in the organization do not affect the stress level of the casual employees compared to the permanent employees of the Local Government Unit of Lubao.

While among the casual employees, it was found that managing change has a strong positive significant relationship between the job and career satisfaction factor ($r=.518$, $p\text{-value} = .000$) which indicates that as the employees are satisfied with their jobs, the more they can see effectiveness on how the organization deals with changes. Kuokkanen et al. (2009) conducted a study and findings showed that organizational changes have direct effect to the job satisfaction of the employees and to cope up with these certain changes; attention must be given to the personnel management. The casual employees in this study revealed high level of job and career satisfaction despite of having average perception of organization’s effective in managing change. With this regard, the Local Government of Lubao should sustain the satisfaction level of the employees by improving their strategies on how to properly handle and manage changes in the organization. Unlike with the results found in the permanent employees wherein managing change has no significant relationship with job and career satisfaction ($r=.044$, $p\text{-value} = .685$) which signifies that changes in the organization does not affect their satisfaction with their jobs.

Moreover, findings showed that managing change domain has a significant relationship between the casual employees’ general well-being ($r=.504$, $p\text{-value} = .000$). This indicates that as the perception of the casual employees on how the organization adapts and deals with changes increases, the level of their psychological well-being and general physical health aspects also increases. It has been found in the study of Flovik et al. (2019) that changes in the organization and how the people see the changes has significant relationship with the employees’ health. In this study, the casual employees were found to have high level of general well-being and an average level of

perception to managing change. This signifies that the respondents can handle their holistic well-being much better compared to the permanent employees despite of the organization not having a high level of effectiveness in dealing with changes because findings found that managing change has no significant relationship with the general well-being ($r=.161$, $p\text{-value}=.136$) of the permanent employees. Since the casual employees in the Local Government Unit of Lubao are mostly younger than the permanent employees, their health issues are more bearable than the latter wherein World Health Organization (2018) stated that as people age, they are more likely to experience several health conditions at the same time.

Significant relationship was also found between managing change and home-work interface domain ($r=.444$, $p\text{-value}=.000$) among casual employees. Unlike with the findings of the study to the permanent employees wherein it was found that managing change and home-work interface domain ($r=.140$, $p\text{-value}=.198$) has no significant relationship with each other. Williams (2021) suggested that the organization should handle change initiative by considering the balance of personal and career lives of the employees to avoid and overcome resistance to change. In this study, casual employees have an average level of work-life balance and perception of managing change. Hence, it is suggested that the organization should promote a well-balanced work-life among its employees in order to help them deal with the changes in the local government.

Furthermore, managing change has significant positive correlations with control at work ($r=.291$, $p\text{-value}=.007$) and working conditions ($r=.406$, $p\text{-value}=.000$) among casual employees. Flovik (2019) suggested that changes in the organizations significantly affect the psychosocial factors of the employees such as the control at work and working conditions in the organizations. In this study, respondents scored average in both of these domains. Findings suggested that casual employees should be provided with rights to be involved with the decision making that concerns their jobs and must have good working conditions in order to do their job effectively. Unlike with the findings of this study to the permanent employees wherein managing change was found to have no significant relationship with control at work ($r=.067$, $p\text{-value}=.537$) and working conditions ($r=.149$, $p\text{-value}=.167$).

Since most of the casual employees in the organization have lower years in service compared to the permanent employees, they are not used with the changes happening in the Local Government due to the changes in leadership and demands of the job through the years. The adjustment period causes them to affect their levels of perceived quality of working life in the organization.

Table 4 revealed that there are positive significant correlations among permanent and casual employees from the different psychosocial factors of quality of working life. It is shown in the table that among all the factors, achieving goals domain resulted a higher significant relationship with the home-work interface ($r=.225$, $p\text{-value}=.036$) of the permanent employees. Significant relationship between home-work interface and achieving goals indicates that when the employees experience control and balance in their professional and personal lives, their perception towards their organization as an agency which supports achievement and improvement in aiming for goals increases.

Table 4
Relationship between Achieving Goals Domain and Perceived Quality of Working Life per Employment Status

r	p-value	PERMANENT			Psychosocial Factors of WRQoL	r	p-value	CASUAL		
		Interpretation	Decision	Conclusion				Interpretation	Decision	Conclusion
.148	.171	Positive weak relationship	Accept Ho	Not Significant	General Well- Being (GWB)	.454**	.000	Positive moderate relationship	Reject Ho	Significant
.225*	.036	Positive weak relationship	Reject Ho	Significant	Home – Work Interface (HWI)	.338**	.002	Positive moderate relationship	Reject Ho	Significant
.209	.052	Positive weak relationship	Accept Ho	Not Significant	Job and Career Satisfaction (JCS)	.443**	.000	Positive moderate relationship	Reject Ho	Significant
.205	.057	Positive weak relationship	Accept Ho	Not Significant	Control at Work (CaW)	.019	.866	Positive very weak relationship	Accept Ho	Not Significant
.222*	.039	Positive weak relationship	Reject Ho	Significant	Working Condition (WC)	.379**	.000	Positive moderate relationship	Reject Ho	Significant
.224*	.037	Positive weak relationship	Reject Ho	Significant	Stress at Work (SaW)	.260*	.016	Positive moderate relationship	Reject Ho	Significant

**Correlation Significance at 0.01 (2-tailed)
*Correlation Significance at 0.05 (2-tailed)

The employees will be more productive and motivated to aim for the organizational goals. In the study conducted by Sheppard (2016), balance between personal and work life aspects improve the organizational culture and performance of the respondents to achieve goals. While in this study, the permanent employees were revealed to have an average level of home-work interface and achieving goals domain.

Due to the workloads of the permanent employees, they were not able to fully achieve and coordinate their career and outside lives which is why the organization should focus on this aspect because according to Heathfield (2021), the workplace that encourage the employees to achieve this balance produces motivated, gratified and productive employees which results in fulfilling the mission of the organization. Similar with the results among casual employees as shown in Table 4 wherein achieving goals is significantly correlated with their home-work interface ($r=.225$, $p\text{-value}=.036$). In this study, the casual employees revealed an average level of

home-work interface and achieving goals. With this regard, since they are correlated with each other, organization should promote programs that will complement their lives at work and in their homes.

Moreover, permanent employees were found to have significant relationship with achieving goals and stress at work ($r=.288$, $p\text{-value}=.007$) which signifies that as the organization strive to achieve its goals, the more the employees feel stress at their jobs. Eddleston and Mulki (2015) stated that job stress can be found to permanent and full-time employees. Sometimes the organizations put constant pressure on the employees in accomplishing their organizational goals and this focus made them forget about the welfare of their employees. Hence, in this study, permanent employees were found to have an average level of perception to the organization's effectiveness in achieving goals and a high level of stress at work. This implicates that the organization should develop programs that will lower the stress level of the permanent employees in their work experiences. The same as the results of the casual employees wherein it was found that achieving goals has significant relationship with stress at work ($r=.210$, $p\text{-value}=.053$). When the casual employees feel that the organization is goal-oriented, their level and amount of stress also increases. This is considered as a challenge especially when the goals of the organizations are intimidating.

Furthermore, results revealed that the achieving goals domain of the casual employees has a positive significant relationship with general well-being ($r=.454$, $p\text{-value}=.000$) and job and career satisfaction ($r=.443$, $p\text{-value}=.000$) which are the highest correlations among all the psychosocial factors. This suggests that as the level of perception of the casual employees in aiming for goals increases, the level of their psychological well-being and general physical health aspects and contentment with their jobs also increases. In this study, the level of general well-being of the casual employees is high and an average score in achieving goals. Adriaenssens et al. (2015) found that goal-oriented organization has significant relationship with the well-being of the employees. This means that to be a goal-oriented organization, the local government must maintain the high level of general well-being of the employees. In addition, findings in the study suggested that casual employees have high level of satisfaction towards their job and an average level of perception in having a goal-oriented organization. According to Roy (2021) when the employees are satisfied with their jobs, positive perception to the organization's achievement of goals increases. To have an organization full of motivated employees, the important thing that they should have are satisfied employees who are happy with what they are doing at work. Compared to the findings of the study among permanent employees wherein achieving goals has no significant relationship found between their general well-being ($r=.148$, $p\text{-value}=.171$) and job and career satisfaction ($r=.209$, $p\text{-value}=.052$) which indicates that their holistic well-being and contentment with their jobs is not related with how the organization achieve their goals.

While, working conditions among permanent ($r=.222$, $p\text{-value}=.039$) and casual employees ($r=.379$, $p\text{-value}=.000$) found significant relationship with the achieving goals wherein it implicates that the organization must provide proper working condition to produce productive and motivated employees. Similar with the study of Pomaki et al. (2004) in which working condition is significantly related to the perception of the employees in achieving organizational goals. Since public organizations are different from the private sectors, improving of the working conditions such as the wages depends on the memorandums and laws released by the Department of Budget and Management such as the Local Budget Circular 132 which states the salary schedule of the local government employees for 2021 (Department of Budget and Management, 2021). Also, no significant relationship was found in both permanent ($r=.205$, $p\text{-value}=.057$) and casual employees ($r=.019$, $p\text{-value}=.866$) with their achieving goals domain and control at work wherein their decisions and involvement at work is not related with how they achieve goals.

Table 5 presents that there is a moderate positive relationship between the coordinated teamwork and home-work interface ($r=.363$, $p\text{-value}=.001$) among permanent employees which indicates that when the level of their balance between personal and professional lives of the employees increases, their perception to the organization's work coordination and collaboration of individuals and groups increases. Having a good – work life balance among employees can produce better teamwork and communication. When employees feel that the organization instill culture where the relationship between work and personal life does matter, it can improve the employees' loyalty, commitment and unity with each other (Rampton, 2016).

In an article written by Zucker (2017), an experiment was conducted to Boston Consulting Group wherein teams worked with each other to create a shared goal of having each person have their day off to work by covering for the person who will spend time outside work, findings suggested that employees were reinforced with trust, collaboration and efficiency with their jobs. In this study, findings suggested that permanent employees have average level of home-work interface and coordinated teamwork domains. Since according to Sanfilippo (2020), having a healthy work life balance can produce a greater sense of well-being among the employees, the organization of the respondents must support and take good care of the welfare of the employees inside and outside the work setup.

While in the other domains, results showed that no significant relationship is present among permanent employees with their coordinated teamwork domain and the other domains of quality of work life such as general well-being ($r=.118$, $p\text{-value}=.275$), job and career satisfaction ($r=.167$, $p\text{-value}=.123$), control at work ($r=.157$, $p\text{-value}=.146$) working condition ($r=.194$, $p\text{-value}=.071$) and stress at work ($r=.155$, $p\text{-value}=.152$). In this regard, the perception of the permanent employees of the Local Government Unit of Lubao in having a shared value of collaboration and coordination with each other is not related with their holistic psychological and physical aspects of their well-being, conditions at work, involvement with the decision – making and their level of stress at work.

While among casual employees, table shows several moderate positive correlations among the variables using the $<.05$ and $<.01$ level of significance. It shows that general well-being ($r=.421$, $p\text{-value}=.000$) and job and career satisfaction ($r=.316$, $p\text{-value}=.003$) has

a positive significant relationship with the coordinated teamwork domain wherein it signifies that once the employees feel healthy in all aspects and satisfied with their jobs, their perception towards their organization as customer oriented also increases. In the study conducted by Mierlo (2003), it was found that teamwork domain has significant relationship with the well-being and job satisfaction of the employees. As the team continues to work together, their psychological, health needs and contentment with their careers also improve. In this study, the casual employees have high level of general well-being and job satisfaction. With an average level of coordinated teamwork domain, the organization should focus in maintaining the high satisfaction of the employees with their needs and prospects at work.

Table 5
Relationship between Coordinated Teamwork Domain and Perceived Quality of Working Life per Employment Status

r	p-value	PERMANENT			Psychosocial Factors of WRQoL	r	p-value	CASUAL		
		Interpretation	Decision	Conclusion				Interpretation	Decision	Conclusion
.118	.275	Positive weak relationship	Accept Ho	Not Significant	General Well-Being (GWB)	.421**	.000	Positive moderate relationship	Reject Ho	Significant
.363**	.001	Positive moderate relationship	Reject Ho	Significant	Home – Work Interface (HWI)	.289**	.007	Positive moderate relationship	Reject Ho	Significant
.167	.123	Positive weak relationship	Accept Ho	Not Significant	Job and Career Satisfaction (JCS)	.316**	.003	Positive moderate relationship	Reject Ho	Significant
.157	.146	Positive weak relationship	Accept Ho	Not Significant	Control at Work (CaW)	.005	.963	Positive very weak relationship	Accept Ho	Not Significant
.194	.071	Positive weak relationship	Accept Ho	Not Significant	Working Condition (WC)	.304**	.005	Positive moderate relationship	Reject Ho	Significant
.155	.152	Positive weak relationship	Accept Ho	Not Significant	Stress at Work (SaW)	.262*	.016	Positive moderate relationship	Reject Ho	Significant

**Correlation Significance at 0.01 (2-tailed)
*Correlation Significance at 0.05 (2-tailed)

Furthermore, it shows that home-work interface (r=.289, p-value =.007) and working conditions (r=.304, p-value = .005) are positively correlated with coordinated teamwork. Derrick (2019) also suggested that the perception of teamwork in an organization produced a balanced life between the employees’ personal and work life as well as their working conditions at work. With this study, casual employees have an average level of home-work interface and working condition as well as the coordinated teamwork domain. Areas for improvement in these aspects are needed to maintain the value of collaboration in the organization. While control at work (r=.262, p-value = .016) domain among them has no significant relationship with coordinated teamwork. Since casual employees in the local government has few involvements and contributions with the decision-making in the workplace compared to permanent employees.

Table 6
Relationship between Customer Orientation Domain and Perceived Quality of Working Life per Employment Status

r	p-value	PERMANENT			Psychosocial Factors of WRQoL	r	p-value	CASUAL		
		Interpretation	Decision	Conclusion				Interpretation	Decision	Conclusion
.045	.681	Positive very weak relationship	Accept Ho	Not Significant	General Well-Being (GWB)	.396**	.000	Positive moderate relationship	Reject Ho	Significant
.131	.225	Positive weak relationship	Accept Ho	Not Significant	Home – Work Interface (HWI)	.452**	.000	Positive moderate relationship	Reject Ho	Significant
.091	.400	Positive very weak relationship	Accept Ho	Not Significant	Job and Career Satisfaction (JCS)	.490**	.000	Positive moderate relationship	Reject Ho	Significant
.109	.313	Positive very weak relationship	Accept Ho	Not Significant	Control at Work (CaW)	.226*	.038	Positive weak relationship	Reject Ho	Significant
.106	.329	Positive very weak relationship	Accept Ho	Not Significant	Working Condition (WC)	.496**	.000	Positive moderate relationship	Reject Ho	Significant
.188	.081	Positive weak relationship	Accept Ho	Not Significant	Stress at Work (SaW)	.041	.708	Positive very weak relationship	Accept Ho	Not Significant

**Correlation Significance at 0.01 (2-tailed)
*Correlation Significance at 0.05 (2-tailed)

Table 6 shows that there is no significant relationship found between customer orientation domain of the permanent employees and all of the psychosocial factors in quality of work life such as general well-being (r=.045, p-value = .681), home -work interface (r= .131, p-value = .225), control at work (r=.109, p-value = .313), working conditions (r=.106, p-value = .329) and stress at work (r=.188, p-value =.081). This means that these factors are not related with their perception towards the organization’s support in having an effective customer orientation. Since most of the permanent employees of the Local Government Unit of Lubao have been in the government

industry for a long time and carry bigger responsibilities, they know and practice how public service works and what is the goal of the agency which is to serve, identify and meet the needs of the people. Government service exists to serve the people and members the other of the community. It is available to all especially people within its jurisdiction (Babones, 2013).

However, among the factors, home-work interface and stress at work scored higher levels which signify that the permanent employees engage more with the customers and promote an effective customer orientation in the organization once they experience the right balance inside and outside their work and produced lower stress level while they are in their jobs.

The benefits of the customer centered organizations are not only limited to private companies but also to the government sectors. Public agencies can gain a lot by putting the needs and wants of the citizens. This can benefit not only the public but also its employees (Emidio, et al. 2017). Compared to permanent employees, customer orientation domain among casual employees has a positive moderate significant relationship with almost all the domains of their perceived quality of working life. Among all of the domains, home- work interface ($r=.452$, $p\text{-value}=000$), job and career satisfaction ($r=.490$, $p\text{-value}=.000$) and working conditions ($r=.496$, $p\text{-value}=.000$) showed higher level of significance with customer orientation which implicates that when the casual employees feel that they are satisfied with their life inside and outside work, contented with what their jobs and fulfilled with their workplace environment and conditions, their values towards their organization as customer-oriented also increases. Kaligian (2021) stated that proper work – life balance produces happy employees and these employees are motivated to engage with customers using a positive attitude. While unlike with this study, Karatepe and Douri (2012) suggested no significant relationship between the employees’ job satisfaction and working condition to their customer orientation which signifies that the variables do not affect each other.

Moreover, customer orientation was also found to have significant relationship with control at work ($r=.226$, $p\text{-value} = .038$) and general well-being ($r=.421$, $p\text{-value}=000$) wherein it means that the casual employees must be equipped with decision making skills and have proper holistic well-being to be more customer-oriented. While in this study, the casual employees have an average level of control at work whereas it signifies that they have minimal contributions with the decisions that affects their jobs. The organization should also focus in the general well-being of the employees since it is found by Lotich in 2018 that well-being of the employees in an organization results in higher engagement towards the clients, co-workers and the organization.

Findings of this study suggested that compared to the permanent employees, casual employees in the Local Government Unit of Lubao are mostly the younger employees in the municipality, they have the vigor to engage more with the customers which is visible to the results of the domains of their quality of work life. They are motivated to do their jobs efficiently since they are not yet secured with their employment status and are rooting for promotions. They put their heart in their sleeves in serving the customers since this is the true meaning of public service. This is why the results showed that there is no significant relationship in the customer orientation domain and the level of stress at work ($r=.041$, $p\text{-value}=.708$) of the casual employees.

Table 7
Relationship between Cultural Strength Domain and Perceived Quality of Working Life per Employment Status

r	p-value	PERMANENT			Psychosocial Factors of WRQoL	r	p-value	CASUAL		
		Interpretation	Decision	Conclusion				Interpretation	Decision	Conclusion
.156	.148	Positive weak relationship	Accept Ho	Not Significant	General Well-Being (GWB)	.445**	.000	Positive moderate relationship	Reject Ho	Significant
.162	.134	Positive weak relationship	Accept Ho	Not Significant	Home – Work Interface (HWI)	.533**	.000	Positive strong relationship	Reject Ho	Significant
.105	.331	Positive very weak relationship	Accept Ho	Not Significant	Job and Career Satisfaction (JCS)	.551**	.000	Positive strong relationship	Reject Ho	Significant
.160	.140	Positive weak relationship	Accept Ho	Not Significant	Control at Work (CaW)	.421**	.000	Positive moderate relationship	Reject Ho	Significant
.166	.124	Positive weak relationship	Accept Ho	Not Significant	Working Condition (WC)	.477**	.000	Positive moderate relationship	Reject Ho	Significant
.068	.534	Positive very weak relationship	Accept Ho	Not Significant	Stress at Work (SaW)	-.050	.653	Negative very weak relationship	Accept Ho	Not Significant

**Correlation Significance at 0.01 (2-tailed)

*Correlation Significance at 0.05 (2-tailed)

Table 7 shows that there is no significant relationship between the cultural strength domain and all of the factors of the perceived quality of working life among the permanent employees of the Local Government Unit of Lubao which includes the general well-being ($r=.156$, $p\text{-value}=.148$), home-work interface ($r=.162$, $p\text{-value} = .134$), job and career satisfaction ($r=.105$, $p\text{-value}= .331$), control at work ($r=.160$, $p\text{-value} = .140$), working condition ($r=.166$, $p\text{-value} = .124$) and stress at work ($r= .068$, $p\text{-value} = .534$). The perception of the permanent employees with regards to the strength of the organizational culture which the people agree on values and beliefs of the agency is not related with any of the domains. However, among all the no significant relationships, working condition and home-work interface scored higher which indicates that the high cultural strength of the local government unit affects the work experiences of the permanent employees which made them feel satisfied with their work environment and contented with their balancing in lives.

The organization should still improve their programs in these aspects because the profitability of the Local Government also depends with their cultural strength because Racelis (2010) conducted a research paper in the Philippine Banking Sector wherein results showed a significant and positive correlation between their profitability and the bank's culture strength.

Moreover, positive correlations were shown in the findings among casual employees. The table presents that home-work interface ($r=.533$, $p\text{-value} = .000$) and career and job satisfaction ($r = .551$, $p\text{-value} = .000$) have positive significant relationship with the cultural strength of the organization. The cultural strength is the shared values and beliefs which the organization has. Having a better work – life balance and contentment with the job can also produce a positive cultural strength in the organization. In the study of Chipunza & Malo (2017) to academic professionals, it was found that positive perceptions of the organizational culture showed increase in job satisfaction and work-life balance. This is similar with the findings of the study wherein high level of job satisfaction and work-life balance was found among the casual employees and this leads to high level of perception towards the strength of their organizational culture.

Cultural strength domain and general well-being ($r= .445$, $p\text{-value} = .000$) was also found to have a positive significant relationship. In the article written by Martin (2020), employees' well-being affects their perception of cultural strength wherein organizations with culture grounded in holistic wellness have employees who are more inspired, strategic, productive and resilient because a strong physical, emotional and mental health can help make success possible. In this study, the casual employees have high level of general well-being and cultural strength which indicates that the respondents are satisfied with their holistic well-being which in turn strengthens the organization's culture. Moreover, the working condition ($r=4.77$, $p\text{-level} = .000$) has found to have a significant correlation between the cultural strength of the organization. Heathfield (2020) suggested that workplace environment and other working conditions of an employee can strengthen an organization's culture. In this study, the respondents have an average level of agreeableness in their working condition and a high level of cultural strength. Also, control at work ($r=.477$, $p\text{-level} = .000$) is positively correlated to their cultural strength. Having contributions to the decision-making that affects the job can also increase the perception of the employees with the organization's cultural strength. Lastly, in this study, the level of stress at work ($r= -.050$, $p\text{-level} = .653$) has no significant relationship between the cultural strength domain.

Based on the findings of the study wherein it shows positive correlations, it is suggested that there is a positive significant relationship between the level of quality of working life and perception of the organizational culture of the permanent and casual employees. It indicates that as the level of their good experiences and attitude at work increases, their insights with the shared values and beliefs in the organization also increases. Similar with the study of Rahmawati and Setiawati (2017), Valizadeh and Ghahremani (2012) and Ruggiero et al. (2011), findings revealed in their studies that significant correlation was found between the quality of working – life and organizational culture of the employees.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the researcher therefore concludes the following:

There is no significant relationship between the perceived quality of working life and the organizational culture among the permanent employees.

There is significant relationship between perceived quality of working life and the organizational culture among the casual employees.

Based on the findings and conclusions of the study, the researcher suggests and recommends the following:

The researchers suggest further research on interventions to improve work-life quality based on the study's findings.

Organizations must be aware of the importance of the perceived quality of working life among employees since their welfare affects how they see and perceive their organization's values and beliefs.

Employees should look after and understand each other since their beliefs and experiences vary with their situations in their personal and working life.

For test developers in the industry, they may develop a Filipino questionnaire designed for the government employees specifically in perceived quality of working life and organizational culture.

For future researchers in the field of Organizational Psychology, they may conduct more researches in the local government industry in the Philippines since few studies are conducted. They may correlate other variables with the quality of work-life and organizational culture like job performance and emotional intelligence.

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